

Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools

RDA Recommendation

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Authors: Francis P Crawley, Rory Macneil, Adam Vials Moore, Hea Lim Rhee, RDA OfR Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools WG members

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Abstract: The digital research data infrastructure landscape comprises a myriad of tools for managing and sharing research data during various stages of the research data lifecycle (RDL). Such research tools vary widely depending on data type, user requirement, provider, and subject area. In the context of the Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools Working Group (WG), research tools enable researchers to perform one or more operations, typically on data, and often with data as the output. Tools are usually intended for use by humans. In this context we are explicitly excluding physical instruments.

The diversity and variety of research tools can prove overwhelming and challenging for stakeholders working within the digital research data ecosystem to understand, navigate, and select the most appropriate tool to meet their needs and objectives. The categorisation of research tools, based on their features, functionalities and how they interoperate, remains unclear. In many cases, research tools are not interoperable, often leading to siloed working within organisations and disciplines, thereby limiting the scope of research and the ability to share and reuse data.

This WG aimed to address these challenges by: (i) categorising different types of research tools; and, (ii) mapping different types of research tools to the RDL based on their features and functionalities. The WG produced a categorisation schema of research tool types that includes terminologies, definitions and associated metadata describing features and functionalities of different tool types. In order to ensure the categorisation schema of tool types is accessible, engaging, and interactive, the WG has produced a visual online map of the digital research tool landscape which serves as a dynamic prototype to be further developed in the future.

Impact:

The map of the landscape of digital research tools landscape created by the WG, which has been given the name 'the MaLDReTH model, is intended to serve as a reference and guide for people and organizations that are designing, adopting and implementing research tools and infrastructure. This include developers of tools and infrastructure, organizations which are procuring tools and infrastructure, and research data managers and administrators. It also includes funders of research infrastructure. In addition to serving as a reference and guide for components of research infrastructure, the MaLDReTH model should encourage good practice in terms of integrated approaches to deployment of tools and infrastructure, interoperability between tools, and stimulation of streamlined flows of data and metadata between tools. In all these respects, it has the potential to have a profound and far-reaching impact on the development of research infrastructure and, through that, research productivity and researcher experiences.

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RDA webpage: <https://www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-ofr-mapping-landscape-digital-research-tools-wg/activity/>

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Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools: Recommendation Package

Working Group name: [RDA-OfR Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools](#)

Working Group co-chairs: Emmanuel Adamolekun ([0000-0003-2992-5448](#)), Francis P. Crawley ([0000-0002-6893-5916](#)), Rory Macneil ([0000-0002-8429-096X](#)), Adam Vials Moore ([0000-0002-2085-1908](#)) and Hea Lim Rhee ([0000-0002-4171-5710](#))

Assisting co-chairs: Marcelo Garcia [0000-0002-2927-2371](#) & Richard Pitts [0000-0002-2037-3360](#)

Working Group Facilitator and Editor: Connie Clare ([0000-0002-4369-196X](#))

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Introduction and Impact

The digital research data infrastructure landscape comprises a myriad of tools for managing and sharing research data during various stages of the research data lifecycle (RDL). Such research tools vary widely depending on data type, user requirement, provider, and subject area. In the context of the Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools Working Group (WG), research tools enable researchers to perform one or more operations, typically on data, and often with data as the output. Tools are usually intended for use by humans. In this context we are explicitly excluding physical instruments.

The diversity and variety of research tools can prove overwhelming and challenging for stakeholders working within the digital research data ecosystem to understand, navigate, and select the most appropriate tool to meet their needs and objectives. The categorisation of research tools, based on their features, functionalities and how they interoperate, remains unclear. In many cases, research tools are not interoperable, often leading to siloed working within organisations and disciplines, thereby limiting the scope of research and the ability to share and reuse data.

This WG aimed to address these challenges by: (i) categorising different types of research tools; and, (ii) mapping different types of research tools to the RDL based on their features and functionalities. The WG produced a categorisation schema (a conceptual framework) of research tool types that includes terminologies, definitions, and associated metadata describing features and functionalities of different tool types. In order to ensure the categorisation schema of tool types is accessible, engaging, and interactive, the WG has produced a visual online map of the digital research tool landscape which serves as a dynamic prototype to be further developed in the future.

Adoption Use Cases

To our knowledge, this RDA WG is the first initiative of its kind to categorise different types of research tools with a primary focus on their utility within the RDL. Providing the global research data community with an interactive map of the digital research data tool landscape that can be navigated according to the RDL represents a novel approach to characterising the research data ecosystem. The deliverables produced by this WG aim to provide value and impact for the following adopters:

Adopter	Value/Impact
Researchers (e.g., data creators and users)	To understand, navigate, and select suitable research tools for managing and sharing data by providing information about their functionalities, relevance, and applicability to the various stages of the RDL.
Data support professionals (e.g., data managers)	To gain improved understanding of the digital research data infrastructure landscape, and become better equipped with essential knowledge of different types of research tools to provide relevant support, training, and education.
Open Science/Research/Data Commons professionals	To understand the features, functionalities, and interoperability of different types of research tools that can be used within diverse marketplaces or ‘commons’ for data and services.
Tool developers/providers	To: (i) understand the different research tools operating within the digital research data landscape; and, (ii) improve tool features, functionalities, harmonisation, and interoperability to enhance data management and sharing practice.
Research performing organisations	To make informed recommendations at the organisational policy level to staff regarding appropriate types of research tools for the management and sharing of research data.
Publishers	To make informed recommendations to authors and journal editors regarding appropriate types of research tools for the

	management, publication, and sharing of data associated with journal manuscripts.
Funders	To make informed recommendations to researchers and project managers based on data management plans for funded research.

Potential Adopters

- The California Digital Library and Research Space are recipients of a US National Science Foundation grant to hold a workshop on the topic of ‘Vertical Tool Interoperability’. The MaLDReth model is included as a core structuring element for the workshop, around which issues relating to interoperability between tools used in different stages of the research data lifecycle can be discussed. The workshop will take place in late 2024 or early 2025..
- JISC, the UK digital, data and technology agency focused on tertiary education, research and innovation, is interested in using the MaLDReth model as a reference for policies relating to recommendations and support for research tools and services.
- Discussion with the GORC II WG is scheduled to explore synergies and possible integration between the MaLDReth model at the Services and Tools Element of the GORC model. The first step in this process will take place in September/October 2024, with an initial exploration of mapping between the two models.

Deliverable 1: The creation of a research data lifecycle (RDL) model and crosswalk to existing models

Executive Summary

As there is not one accepted universal Research Data Lifecycle (RDL) model, the first deliverable by the [RDA-OfR Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools Working Group \(WG\)](#) involved the creation of a harmonised RDL that could be used as the foundational framework for underpinning later work on the categorisation and characterisation of digital research tools.

To achieve this, a landscape review was carried out to identify a list of existing RDLs. A qualitative analysis process was conducted to determine the top five best characterised and most comprehensive RDLs. Their stages and definitions were aligned using a semantic distance methodology over an etymological/taxonomic net to produce the Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools Harmonised ([MaLDReth](#)) RDL model.

Documentation

☰ D1_The creation of a harmonised research data lifecycle (RDL) model and crosswalk to e...

Deliverable 2: The identification, categorisation, and mapping of different types of research tools: A categorisation schema

Executive Summary

The second deliverable by the [RDA-OfR Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools Working Group \(WG\)](#) involved the creation of a categorisation schema of digital research tools.

The first phase involved a comprehensive landscape review, conducted over five months (from September 2023 to January 2024), whereby several task groups convened during virtual meetings, plus an extended in person working meeting during the RDA's 21st Plenary in Salzburg, to collate a list of representative digital research tools used during each of the 12 stages of the [MaLDReTH RDL model](#). The number of representative tools listed for each RDL stage varied in length, from four to five tools in the shortest list and 40+ tools in the longest.

The second phase, carried out by a subgroup of four WG members from January to April 2024, involved validating the lists of tools and identifying common categories (types) of tools used during each RDL stage. Due to time constraints, a maximum of three tool categories were identified for each RDL stage. During the final step, the subgroup identified a maximum of three individual digital research tools that serve as representative examples for each tool category.

Documentation

☰ D2_The identification, categorisation, and mapping of different types of research tools: A c...

Deliverable 3: The creation of a preliminary structural framework for an online open access 'map of the digital research tool landscape'

Executive Summary

The final deliverable of the [RDA-OfR Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools Working Group \(WG\)](#) undertakes the necessary foundational work required to create a preliminary structural framework for an online open access 'map of the digital research tool landscape'. In essence, this 'map' is an open access autonomous relational database hosted by the RDA

Foundation (as a legal entity on behalf of the RDA), owned by the community, and powered by Oracle for Software. This arrangement has been discussed and agreed by the RDA and Oracle for Research.

The database, navigable by research data lifecycle stage, contains searchable information (e.g., features, functionalities, interoperability) about different types of digital research tools, and allows for ongoing community curation and further development.

Based on [Deliverable 1](#) (The creation of a harmonised research data lifecycle (RDL) model and crosswalk to existing models) and [Deliverable 2](#) (The identification, categorisation, and mapping of different types of research tools: A categorisation schema), this deliverable presents a prototype for the database in addition to recommendations for its long-term maintenance, sustainability, and adoption.

The idea is that this tool prototype will be further developed and implemented by a follow-on RDA WG, considering the recommendations detailed in this deliverable to ensure the final database remains up to date with newly emerging types of digital research tools and evolves with the ever-changing digital research data infrastructure landscape.

Documentation

☰ D3_The creation of a preliminary structural framework for an online open access ‘map of t...

Tool Prototype:

<https://adamvialsmoore-jisc.shinyapps.io/r-prot>

Recommendations and Future Work

Recommendations

Based on the findings and feedback gathered during the development and community engagement processes, the following recommendations are proposed:

Adoption and Integration

1. Facilitate and encourage widespread adoption of the tool by promoting the tool’s value for research institutions, data management platforms, and relevant professional networks. Develop targeted outreach strategies to engage different stakeholder groups

and highlight the tool's benefits, such as live demonstrations, webinars, conference presentations and posters.

2. Integrate the tool with existing digital research infrastructures to enhance its accessibility and usability. In particular, discuss synergies and potential integration with the Services and Tools Element of the GORC Model. Collaborate with other research tool developers and platform providers to facilitate seamless integration and data interoperability.
3. Identify an appropriate hosting platform for the tool. Since hosting costs will be minimal, it should be possible to identify a viable solution. Discuss with the Secretariat the possibility of hosting on the RDA website.

Continuous Improvement

4. Establish a process for regularly updating the tool's database to include new and emerging digital research tools. Monitor trends and advancements in digital research tools to ensure the tool remains current and relevant.
5. Continuously solicit feedback from users throughout the development and implementation process to identify areas for improvement and potential new features for user-driven enhancement. Implement a feedback loop to incorporate user suggestions and enhancements in future iterations of the tool.

Expanding Functionality

6. Enhance the tool's search and filtering capabilities to provide users with more granular control over their searches. Implement advanced filtering options based on specific criteria such as tool functionality, research domain, and compatibility/interoperability with other tools.
7. Explore opportunities for integrating the tool with other research management and data sharing platforms. Develop API functionalities to enable seamless data exchange and interoperability with external systems.

Educational and Support Resources

8. Develop comprehensive user guides and tutorials to assist users in navigating and utilising the tool effectively. Provide step-by-step instructions and best practice recommendations to enhance user experience based on stakeholder value and interest.

9. Organise generic training sessions and workshops to educate users about the tool's features and functionalities. Provide hands-on, practical training opportunities to help users become proficient in using the tool for their individual research data management needs.

Future Directions

Several strategic initiatives and future directions are proposed to build on the success of Deliverable 3, and ensure the ongoing development and impact of the online tool.

Database Expansion

Continuously expand the tool's database to include different types of digital research tools with relevant examples. Collaborate with tool developers and research communities to identify and categorise new tools.

Global Outreach

Promote the tool globally and establish partnerships with key stakeholders. Engage with international research communities and organisations to promote the tool and encourage global adoption. Establish partnerships with key stakeholders to facilitate knowledge sharing and collaboration.

Sustainability Plan

Develop a sustainability plan to ensure the long-term maintenance and support of the tool. Explore funding opportunities and collaborative ventures to secure the necessary resources for ongoing development.

Note: There has been ongoing discussion within the WG about the choice of software underpinning the online tool. The prototype presented herein currently uses open source software on open storage/facilities. It's coded entirely in R / Shiny with non commercial libraries. The WG should consider the future production status of the tools developed, and investigate the advantages and disadvantages of using different software. For example, should the final application be open or closed? What about the schema for the information stored? Should the storage layer be in a modern, stable environment like Oracle OCI or remain as a portable SQLite file?

Innovative Features

Investigate the potential for incorporating advanced features such as machine learning algorithms to provide personalised tool recommendations. Explore the integration of

visualisation tools to enhance the user experience and provide insights into the research data lifecycle.

Next steps

Members of the WG and external collaborators are in the process of establishing a follow-on RDA WG to continue the development of the online tool. The focus of the follow-on WG will be to:

- **Continue development of the tool:** This will include the adding more information about the attributes of different types of digital research tools, such as whether they are open or closed source, disciplinary or agnostic, and, interoperable or not.
- **Explore sustainability of the model:** This will include ways in which it can be kept up to date to reflect changes in technology, development of new research tools, changes in research practices, etc. Also provide options for continuing support for the model, which could include participation by various RDA groups and external organisations and/or communities.
- **Collaboration with RDA groups working on the Global Open Research Commons (GORC):** As the tool prototype was developed in recent months, the Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools WG had discussions with the [Global Open Research Commons IG](#) and [GORC International Model WG](#) about the synergies in work and potential for collaboration. Task Group 5 of the GORC International WG has undertaken an extensive [literature review](#) and released a [Commons Attributes Model \(Version 0.5\)](#) that identifies a suite of services and tools that will inform the work of this WG. Efforts to describe the features, functionality, and interoperability of different types of research tools will complement the development of the 'Commons Integration Roadmap' (GORC WG Deliverable) by providing key information about different types of research tools, and highlighting areas for the improvement of their interoperability and user experience.

Conclusion

Deliverable 3 has successfully developed a prototype for an interactive online tool that maps digital research tools to the research data lifecycle.

This tool provides significant value to researchers, data managers, tool developers, research organisations, funders, and publishers. The comprehensive feedback from the RDA community has been instrumental in refining the tool and ensuring its relevance and usability.

The recommendations and future directions outlined in this deliverable report offer a roadmap for continued development, adoption, and impact. By leveraging the work achieved by the current WG, as well as the insights and feedback gathered for the creation of this deliverable, a follow-on RDA WG is well-positioned to enhance the tool's functionality and expand its reach, ultimately contributing to the advancement of digital research data management and sharing practices.

For further details, please refer to the [RDA-OfR Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools WG](#).

Deliverable 1: The creation of a harmonised research data lifecycle (RDL) model and crosswalk to existing models

Working Group name: [RDA-OfR Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools](#)

Working Group co-chairs: Emmanuel Adamolekun ([0000-0003-2992-5448](#)), Francis P. Crawley ([0000-0002-6893-5916](#)), Rory Macneil ([0000-0002-8429-096X](#)), Adam Vials Moore ([0000-0002-2085-1908](#)) and Hea Lim Rhee ([0000-0002-4171-5710](#))

Assisting co-chairs: Marcelo Garcia [0000-0002-2927-2371](#) & Richard Pitts [0000-0002-2037-3360](#)

Working Group Facilitator and Editor: Connie Clare ([0000-0002-4369-196X](#))

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The creation of a research data lifecycle (RDL) model and crosswalk to existing models

Executive Summary

As there is not one accepted universal Research Data Lifecycle (RDL) model, the first deliverable by the [RDA-OfR Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools Working Group \(WG\)](#) involved the creation of a harmonised RDL that could be used as the foundational framework for underpinning later work on the categorisation and characterisation of digital research tools.

To achieve this, a landscape review was carried out to identify a list of existing RDLs. A qualitative analysis process was conducted to determine the top five best characterised and most comprehensive RDLs. Their stages and definitions were aligned using a semantic distance methodology over an etymological/taxonomic net to produce the Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools Harmonised (MaLDR_eTH) RDL model.

Aims and Objectives

Research data management (RDM) is a critical aspect of modern scientific endeavours, ensuring the integrity, reproducibility, and long-term preservation of valuable research outputs. However, the lack of a universally accepted RDL model poses challenges to establishing standardised practices and facilitating effective RDM across various research domains.

The Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools WG examined and identified different stages of the research data lifecycle (RDL), and developed a harmonised RDL to serve as the foundational framework for categorising and characterising various types of digital research tools. Since numerous different RDL models exist that have been conceptualised for specific research paradigms and audiences, the WG conducted a landscape review to research and consult existing models and identify common stages of the RDL for use as the framework to guide the research tool categorisation. A harmonised RDL was created to provide a common language and reference point for researchers, data stewards, and tool

developers alike, facilitating collaboration and interoperability within the research data ecosystem. Each RDL stage is supported by definitions. The WG created a crosswalk to demonstrate connections between the chosen model and existing models.

Methodology and Results

A comprehensive landscape review was conducted to identify existing RDL models from various sources, including scholarly publications, institutional guidelines, and domain-specific best practices. Initially, [20 candidate RDLs](#) were identified, representing diverse perspectives and approaches to RDM (Fig. 1).

A qualitative analysis process was undertaken to assess the comprehensiveness, clarity, and applicability of these candidate RDLs across different research domains. This evaluation considered factors such as the completeness of the lifecycle stages, the preciseness of stage definitions, and overall suitability of the model for addressing the nuances of RDM in various disciplines.

The [top five best characterised and most comprehensive RDL models](#) were selected for harmonisation (Table 1). To reconcile any potential overlaps, gaps, or inconsistencies in the terminology and concepts, stages of each selected RDL model were aligned using a semantic distance methodology over an etymological/taxonomic net (Fig. 2). This approach, inspired by the work of [Thompson et al., 2020](#), leveraged etymological and taxonomic networks to align 12 common stages and definitions of each RDL model, ensuring conceptual coherence and consistency.

The outcome of this harmonisation process was the MaLDReTH RDL (Fig. 3 & 4), a synthesised model that captures the comprehensive aspects of the 5 selected RDLs. The MaLDReTH RDL model represents a standardised and harmonised framework for RDM, facilitating effective collaboration and tool development across various research domains.

By providing a common language and reference point, the MaLDReTH RDL model addresses a long-standing gap in the RDM landscape, promoting data stewardship, reproducibility, and the long-term preservation of valuable research outputs. For the purpose of this WG, the MaLDReTH RDL model serves as the foundational framework for the production of [Deliverable 2](#) (The identification, categorisation, and mapping of different types of research tools: A categorisation schema) and [Deliverable 3](#) (The creation of a preliminary structural framework for an online open access 'map of the digital research tool landscape'), enabling the systematic categorisation, characterisation, and mapping of digital research tools.

Table 1. Top five Research Data Lifecycle (RDL) models selected for harmonisation.

Research Data Lifecycle (RDL)	Source	Rationale
	DCC Data Curation Lifecycle Digital Data Curation Centre	Focused on curation, workflow, data management centric.
	RDMkit Data Life Cycle ELIXIR	Popular, well known, simple, uses commonly referenced stages.
	Best Practice Data Life Cycle Approaches for the Life Sciences EMBL-ABR Data Life Cycle Workshop Series	Best practice RDL for researchers in the Life Sciences/Bioinformatics.
	Research Data Framework (RDaF) National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST)	Broad, discipline agnostic.
	The Research Data Lifecycle University College London (UCL)	Comprehensive, uses commonly referenced stages of the lifecycle, useful references to activities relating to stages.

Figure 1. Qualitative analysis, selection and alignment of 20 Research Data Lifecycle (RDL) Models to produce the MaLDReTH model.

Figure 2. Research Data Lifecycle (RDL) stage alignment using a semantic distance methodology over an etymological/taxonomic net.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3. Initial Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools Harmonised (MaLDReTH) Research Data Lifecycle Model (RDL) (a) and crosswalk to existing models created using Figma (b).

The MaLDReTH
Research Data Lifecycle

Figure 4. Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools Harmonised (MaLDReTH) Research Data Lifecycle (RDL) Model created using GraphViz in the R prototype app.

Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools Harmonised (MaLDR_eTH) Research Data Lifecycle (RDL) Stages and Definitions

CONCEPTUALISE: To formulate the initial research idea or hypothesis, and define the scope of the research project and the data component/requirements of that project.

PLAN: To establish a structured strategic framework for management of the research project, outlining aims, objectives, methodologies, and resources required for data collection, management and analysis. Data management plans (DMP) should be established for this phase of the lifecycle.

FUND: To identify and acquire financial resources to support the research project, including data collection, management, analysis, sharing, publishing and preservation.

COLLECT: To use predefined procedures, methodologies and instruments to acquire and store data that is reliable, fit for purpose and of sufficient quality to test the research hypothesis.

PROCESS: To make new and existing data analysis-ready. This may involve standardised pre-processing, cleaning, reformatting, structuring, filtering, and performing quality control checks on data. It may also involve the creation and definition of metadata for use during analysis, such as acquiring provenance from instruments and tools used during data collection.

ANALYSE: To derive insights, knowledge, and understanding from processed data. Data analysis involves iterative exploration and interpretation of experimental or computational results, often utilising mathematical models and formulae to investigate relationships between experimental variables. Distinct data analysis techniques and methodologies are applied according to the data type (quantitative vs qualitative).

STORE: To record data using technological media appropriate for processing and analysis whilst maintaining data integrity and security.

Note **COLLECT > PROCESS > ANALYSE > STORE** may be a repeating cycle.

PUBLISH: To release research data in published form for use by others with appropriate metadata for citation (including a unique persistent identifier) based on FAIR principles.

PRESERVE: To ensure the safety, integrity, and accessibility of data for as long as necessary so that data is as FAIR as possible. Data preservation is more than data storage and backup, since data can be stored and backed up without being preserved. Preservation should include curation activities such as data cleaning, validation, assigning preservation metadata, assigning representation information, and ensuring acceptable data structures and file formats. At a minimum, data and associated metadata should be published in a trustworthy digital repository and clearly cited in the accompanying journal article unless this is not possible (e.g. due to the privacy or safety concerns).

SHARE: To make data available and accessible to humans and/or machines. Data may be

shared with project collaborators or published to share it with the wider research community and society at large. Data sharing is not limited to open data or public data, and can be done during various stages of the research data lifecycle. At a minimum, data and associated metadata should be published in a trustworthy digital repository and clearly cited in the accompanying journal article.

ACCESS: To control and manage data access by designated users and reusers. This may be in the form of publicly available published information. Necessary access control and authentication methods are applied.

TRANSFORM: To create new data from the original, for example: (i) by migration into a different format; (ii) by creating a subset, by selection or query, to create newly derived results, perhaps for publication; or, iii) combining or appending with other data

Contributors

	Name	Affiliation	ORCID
1	Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström	Uppsala University / ELIXIR Sweden / National Bioinformatics Infrastructure Sweden (NBIS)	0000-0002-3890-6620
2	Mohammad Akhlaghi	Centro de Estudios de Física del Cosmos de Aragón (CEFCA)	0000-0003-1710-6613
3	Louise Bezuidenhout	Leiden University	0000-0003-4328-3963
4	Francis P. Crawley	Good Clinical Practice Alliance - Europe (GCPA) & Strategic Initiative for Developing Capacity in Ethical Review (SIDCER)	0000-0002-6893-5916
5	Gavin Farrell	ELIXIR (EMBL-EBI)	0000-0001-5166-8551
6	Marcelo Garcia	King Abdullah University of Science and Technology (KAUST)	0000-0002-2927-2371
7	Margareta Hellström	Lund University	0000-0002-4154-2610
8	Malgorzata Lagisz	UNSW Sydney	0000-0002-3993-6127
9	Hea Lim Rhee	Korea Institute of Science and Technology Information (KISTI)	0000-0002-4171-5710
10	Rory Macneil	Research Space	0000-0002-8429-096X
11	Lauren Maxwell	University of Heidelberg, World Health Organization (WHO)	
12	Andrea Medina-Smith	National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST)	0000-0002-1217-701X
13	Richard Pitts	Oracle for Research	0000-0002-2037-3360
14	Marina Razmadze	CHU Sainte-Justine	

ORACLE
for Research

15	Martina Stockhause	German Climate Computing Center (DKRZ)	0000-0001-6636-4972
16	Ville Tenhunen	EGI Foundation	0000-0003-0217-0831
17	Adam Vials Moore	Jisc	0000-0002-2085-1908
18	James Wilson	University College London (UCL)	0000-0002-8546-1142
19	Nina Leonie Weisweiler	Helmholtz Association	0000-0001-6967-9443

Deliverable 2:

The identification, categorisation, and mapping of different types of research tools: A categorisation schema

Working Group name: [RDA-OfR Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools](#)

Working Group co-chairs: Emmanuel Adamolekun ([0000-0003-2992-5448](#)), Francis P. Crawley ([0000-0002-6893-5916](#)), Rory Macneil ([0000-0002-8429-096X](#)), Adam Vials Moore ([0000-0002-2085-1908](#)) and Hea Lim Rhee ([0000-0002-4171-5710](#))

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The identification, categorisation, and mapping of different types of research tools: A categorisation schema

Executive Summary

The second deliverable by the [RDA-OfR Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools Working Group \(WG\)](#) involved the creation of a categorisation schema of digital research tools.

The first phase involved a comprehensive landscape review, conducted over five months (from September 2023 to January 2024), whereby several task groups convened during virtual meetings, plus an extended in person working meeting during the RDA's 21st Plenary in Salzburg, to collate a list of representative digital research tools used during each of the 12 stages of the [MaLDReTH RDL model](#). The number of representative tools listed for each RDL stage varied in length, from four to five tools in the shortest list and 40+ tools in the longest.

The second phase, carried out by a subgroup of four WG members from January to April 2024, involved validating the lists of tools and identifying common categories (types) of tools used during each RDL stage. Due to time constraints, a maximum of three tool categories were identified for each RDL stage. During the final step, the subgroup identified a maximum of three individual digital research tools that serve as representative examples for each tool category.

Aims and Objectives

The WG aimed to conduct a landscape review to identify, categorise, and map different types of digital research tools to the 12 stages of the MaLDReTH RDL model. The objective was to collect examples of individual digital research tools, and to categorise and describe them based on their utility and interoperability.

An overarching aim of this deliverable was to highlight the potential for and current limitations of streamlined flow of research data and metadata throughout the research data lifecycle based on how different types of research tools interoperate. Understanding this is highly valuable in the context of developing the national and international open research commons. In particular, this work aimed to contribute to and build on the work of the RDA's [Global Open Research Commons IG](#) and [GORC International Model WG](#). Task Group 5 of the GORC International WG has undertaken an extensive [literature review](#) and released a [Commons Attributes Model \(Version 0.5\)](#) that identifies a suite of services and tools that informed the work of this WG.

Methodology and Results

Initial Landscape Review

Over five months (from September 2023 to January 2024), several task groups formed to conduct an in-depth landscape review to collect as much information about individual digital tools for each MaLDReTH stage.

The first phase brought more than 30 RDA community members together during virtual meetings, plus an extended in person working meeting during the RDA's 21st Plenary in Salzburg, to collate a list of representative digital research tools used during each of the 12 stages of the MaLDReTH RDL model (Table 1). Initial thought was given to the *openness* (open or closed source), *disciplinary focus* (disciplinary or agnostic), and *interoperability* features and functionalities of each tool. However, time constraints meant this information was beyond the scope of this WG and, therefore, was omitted from its Deliverables.

The participation of numerous and diverse members, who each brought knowledge of particular types of tools and tools categories, helped to ensure that each stage was well populated with relevant examples of digital research tools.

Table 1. Representative list of digital research tools used during stages of the [MaLDReTH Research Data Lifecycle \(RDL\) model](#).

MaLDReTH RDL Stage	No. of tools	MaLDReTH RDL Stage	No. of tools
1. Conceptualise	12	7. Store	47
2. Plan	15	8. Publish	27
3. Fund*	15	9. Preserve	11
4. Collect	48	10. Share	10
5. Process	38	11. Access	4
6. Analyse	10	12. Transform	7

**Fund: After some deliberation, the WG decided to omit 'Fund' from the landscape review since the examples identified were not categorised as digital research tools.*

Categorisation of Digital Research Tools

The next phase, carried out by a subgroup of four WG members, involved validating the lists of individual digital research tools and, from those lists (Table 1), identifying common categories of tools used during each RDL stage. Tool categories were chosen based on consensus and well-known terminologies. Given the time and effort limitation, a maximum of three tool categories were identified for each RDL stage and a short description was provided for each tool category.

Identification of Representative Example Tools

During the final phase, the subgroup identified a maximum of [three individual digital research tools](#) that serve as representative examples for each tool category (Figure 1). Tools that are commonly used to perform tasks during that stage of the RDL and are, therefore, representative of a specific tool category were selected as examples.

Figure 1. Format for the categorisation schema of types of digital research tools and representative example tools.

From January to April 2024, the concentrated effort of this subgroup progressed the deliverable from a state of uncurated ideation to an organised categorisation schema that forms the foundation for [Deliverable 3](#) (The creation of a preliminary structural framework for an online open access ‘map of the digital research tool landscape’).

Contributors

	Name	Affiliation	ORCID
1	Tessa Acar	Flemish Research Data Network (FRDN)	
2	Louise Bezhuidenhout	Leiden University	0000-0003-4328-3963
3	Gemma Buck	University of Oxford	
4	Kwangnam Choi	Korea Institute of Science and Technology Information (KISTI)	
5	Francis P. Crawley	Good Clinical Practice Alliance - Europe (GCPA) & Strategic Initiative for Developing Capacity in Ethical Review (SIDCER)	0000-0002-6893-5916
6	Willeke De Haan	KU Leuven	
7	Laurence El Khouri	Centre national de la recherche scientifique (CNRS)	
8	Marcelo Garcia	King Abdullah University of Science and Technology (KAUST)	0000-0002-2927-2371
9	Daniela Hausen	RWTH Aachen University	0000-0001-9083-0670
10	Tadesse Kassahun Melese	Addis Ababa University	
11	Uwe Konrad	Helmholtz HZDR33	0000-0001-8167-9411
12	Markus Kubin	Helmholtz-Zentrum Berlin für Materialien und Energie	0000-0002-2209-9385
13	Malgorzata Lagisz	UNSW Sydney	0000-0002-3993-6127
14	Andrea Lammert	German Climate Computing Center (DKRZ)	0000-0002-1506-4299

15	Hea Lim Rhee	Korea Institute of Science and Technology Information (KISTI)	0000-0002-4171-5710
16	Pedro Luiz Pizzigatti Corrêa	University of São Paulo	0000-0002-8743-4244
17	Rory Macneil	Research Space	0000-0002-8429-096X
18	Andrea Medina-Smith	National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST)	0000-0002-1217-701X
19	Wolmar Nyberg Åkerström	Uppsala University / ELIXIR Sweden / National Bioinformatics Infrastructure Sweden (NBIS)	0000-0002-3890-6620
20	Richard Pitts	Oracle for Research	0000-0002-2037-3360
21	Barbara Sanchez	TU Wien	
22	James Savage	Te Pūkenga — New Zealand Institute of Skills and Technology	
23	Martina Stockhause	Data Distribution Centre (DDC) of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC)	0000-0001-6636-4972
24	Josh Taillon	National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST)	
25	Ville Tenhunen	EGI Foundation	0000-0003-0217-0831
26	Jung-Ho Um	Korea Institute of Science and Technology Information (KISTI)	0000-0002-8301-8753
27	Vladimir Urosevic	Belit Ltd.	0000-0001-6225-1874
28	Shanmugasundaram Venkataraman	OpenAIRE	0000-0002-3200-2698
29	Adam Vials Moore	Jisc	0000-0002-2085-1908
30	Ramon Wenzel	Minderoo Foundation	
31	James Wilson	University College London	0000-0002-8546-1142

ORACLE
for Research

(UCL)

32	Annemarie Schoenherr	Universität Innsbruck	
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Deliverable 3:

The creation of a preliminary structural framework for an online open access ‘map of the digital research tool landscape’

Working Group name: [RDA-OfR Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools](#)

Working Group co-chairs: Emmanuel Adamolekun ([0000-0003-2992-5448](#)), Francis P. Crawley ([0000-0002-6893-5916](#)), Rory Macneil ([0000-0002-8429-096X](#)), Adam Vials Moore ([0000-0002-2085-1908](#)) and Hea Lim Rhee ([0000-0002-4171-5710](#))

Assisting co-chairs: Marcelo Garcia [0000-0002-2927-2371](#) & Richard Pitts [0000-0002-2037-3360](#)

Working Group Facilitator and Editor: Connie Clare ([0000-0002-4369-196X](#))

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The creation of a preliminary structural framework for an online open access ‘map of the digital research tool landscape’

Executive Summary

The final deliverable of the [RDA-OfR Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools Working Group \(WG\)](#) undertakes the necessary foundational work required to create a preliminary structural framework for an online open access ‘map of the digital research tool landscape’. In essence, this ‘map’ is an open access autonomous relational database hosted by the RDA Foundation (as a legal entity on behalf of the RDA) and owned by the community. This arrangement has been discussed and agreed by the RDA and Oracle for Research.

The database, navigable by research data lifecycle stage, contains searchable information (e.g., features, functionalities, interoperability) about different types of digital research tools, and allows for ongoing community curation and further development.

Based on [Deliverable 1](#) (The creation of a harmonised research data lifecycle (RDL) model and crosswalk to existing models) and [Deliverable 2](#) (The identification, categorisation, and mapping of different types of research tools: A categorisation schema), this deliverable presents a prototype for the database in addition to recommendations for its long-term maintenance, sustainability, and adoption.

The idea is that this tool prototype will be further developed and implemented by a follow-on RDA WG, considering the recommendations detailed in this deliverable to ensure the final database remains up to date with newly emerging types of digital research tools and evolves with the ever-changing digital research data infrastructure landscape.

Aims and Objectives

The WG aimed to create the preliminary structure (a tool prototype) for an open access ‘map of the digital research tool landscape’ navigable by research data lifecycle stage. The ultimate aim was to provide the data community with a dynamic, user-friendly, online database that contains searchable information (e.g., features, functionalities, interoperability) about different types of research tools. The database should also permit ongoing community curation so that it remains up-to-date with newly emerging types of research tools and evolves with the ever-changing digital research data infrastructure landscape. This may include significant data and software-related developments, e.g., Artificial Intelligence (AI).

It was beyond the scope of the current WG to create the final version of the database, however, the objective of Deliverable 3 was to develop a prototype of an autonomous relational database. With the foundational work in place, the idea is that a follow-on RDA

WG will continue to develop and implement the database, considering the recommendations for its long-term maintenance, sustainability, and adoption presented herein.

It is acknowledged that many different ‘maps’ of the digital research infrastructure exist. This particular WG endeavoured to create an open access interactive map that facilitates an intuitive, engaging, and explorative experience of navigating the digital research tool landscape.

Methodology and Results

Tool Prototype Development

Design and Development

From April to July 2024, Adam Vials Moore (WG co-chair), led the prototype design and development process. This was an iterative process that began with outlining the prototype’s information model, core functionalities and user interface requirements (Figures 1 to 5). The design prototype incorporated essential features, such as categorisation, search and filter options. A set of wireframes were developed (Figure 4) to show the general user journey and affordances/interrelation of application routes and actions.

Technical Development

Modern web technologies (initially R/Shiny then python/flask) were used to build the tool, ensuring that it is scalable, responsive and user-friendly. A robust database (Figure 1) was implemented to store information about the different digital research tools and their categorisations, based on [Deliverable 2](#).

Testing and Iteration

Multiple iterations of implementation testing were conducted through demonstrations to identify and resolve technical issues or usability challenges.


```

CREATE TABLE `LifeCycle` (
  `stage` VARCHAR(255) NOT NULL,
  `stagedesc` VARCHAR(255) NOT NULL,
  `stageID` INT NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY(`stageID`)
);
ALTER TABLE
  `LifeCycle` ADD INDEX
  `lifecycle_stage_index`(`stage`);
ALTER TABLE
  `LifeCycle` ADD INDEX
  `lifecycle_stage_index`(`stage`);
CREATE TABLE `Tools` (
  `ToolName` VARCHAR(255) NOT NULL,
  `ToolDesc` VARCHAR(255) NOT NULL,
  `ToolLink` VARCHAR(255) NOT NULL,
  `stage` INT NOT NULL,
  `ToolProvider` VARCHAR(255) NOT NULL,
  `ToolID` INT NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY(`ToolID`)
);
ALTER TABLE
  `Tools` ADD INDEX
  `tools_toolname_index`(`ToolName`);
ALTER TABLE
  `Tools` ADD INDEX
  `tools_toolname_index`(`ToolName`);
CREATE TABLE `SubStage` (

```

```

  `substagename` VARCHAR(255) NOT NULL,
  `substagestage` VARCHAR(255) NOT NULL,
  `substagedesc` VARCHAR(255) NOT NULL,
  `exemplar` INT NULL,
  `substageID` INT NOT NULL,
  PRIMARY KEY(`substageID`)
);
ALTER TABLE
  `SubStage` ADD INDEX
  `substage_substagename_index`(`substagename`);
ALTER TABLE
  `SubStage` ADD INDEX
  `substage_substagename_index`(`substagename`);
ALTER TABLE
  `SubStage` ADD CONSTRAINT
  `substage_substagestage_foreign` FOREIGN
  KEY(`substagestage`) REFERENCES
  `LifeCycle`(`stageID`);
ALTER TABLE
  `Tools` ADD CONSTRAINT
  `tools_stage_foreign` FOREIGN KEY(`stage`)
  REFERENCES `LifeCycle`(`stageID`);
ALTER TABLE
  `SubStage` ADD CONSTRAINT
  `substage_exemplar_foreign` FOREIGN
  KEY(`exemplar`) REFERENCES `Tools`(`ToolID`);

```

Figure 1. Information Schema of Underpinning Information

Figure 2. Unified Modelling Language (UML) for Database User Journey

Figure 3. (a) Graph view of prototype UI/UX journey and (b) Vertical affordance tree view of prototype interactions

Wireframes

Figure 4. Example wireframe for the tool prototype.

See all wireframes: [Data cycle tools vizn wireframes.pdf](#)

Implementation (R/Shiny)

Following on from the work to define the features and functionality of the application, an initial prototype was built in R/Shiny. The prototype used graphViz interpretation to display the MaLDReTH lifecycle. It used a subset of the full RDL tool information to demonstrate display of the information both in text and schema view.

<https://adamvialsmoore-jisc.shinyapps.io/r-proto/>

MaLDReTH Prototype

Figure 5. Open access tool prototype (Model 1), to map different types of digital research tool to the Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools Harmonised (MaLDReTH) Research Data Lifecycle (RDL) model.

From there a User interface approaches have been developed which are displayed below

Model 2 (overview **Figure 6**) is backed by a SQLite database and presents our vision of how data can be maintained from this approach, but the User interface lacks polish.

Figure 6

Model 2 - **Figure 7** interacting with the full life cycle shows the information related in the other windows

Figure 7

By pressing the add tool one can then interact with the SQLite database **Figure 8**. We see this sort of easy editing and data maintenance very important for the future longevity of the project.

Research Data Lifecycle Tools

Explore the research data lifecycle stages and associated tools. Click on a stage to view details and manage tools.

The screenshot shows a web interface for 'Research Data Lifecycle Tools'. It features a 'Full Lifecycle' view on the left and a 'Focused Stage' view on the right. A modal window titled 'Add or Edit Tool' is open in the center, allowing users to input tool details. The modal includes fields for Tool Name, Description, Link, Provider, and Stage. The 'Stage' dropdown is currently set to 'ACCESS'. A 'Save' button is located at the bottom right of the modal. In the background, a table lists various tools with columns for ID, Description, and Link. The 'Standards' tool is highlighted in red.

ID	Description	Link
AAI - Authorize/Authentication Infrastructure	AA-id, access via Gridid provides id	null
API access		null
PETADATA		null
Repositories		overview on https
Standards	https://www.rda-alliance.org/groups/metadata-standards-catalog-working-group.html	https://www.dcc.ac.uk/guidance/standards/metadata/
eg 350k file structure		null

Figure 8

Model 3 **Figure 9** and Model 4 **Figure 10** below show our further user interface experiments. This is ongoing project work which we fully expect to continue into the next working group in this area.

Research Data Lifecycle

Click on a stage to view its substage. Click on a substage to view its examples. Hover over elements to see descriptions. The connections between stages show the flow of the research lifecycle.

How to use this visualization:

1. The main circle shows the stages of the research data lifecycle.
2. Dotted lines with arrows show the connections and flow between stages.
3. Click on any stage (green circles) to view its substages.
4. Click on a substage (light green rectangles) to view its examples.
5. Use the zoom controls in the top right corner to adjust the view.
6. Hover over any element to see its description.
7. Click on a selected stage or substage to deselect it.
8. The orange highlight indicates the currently selected item.

Figure 9 - Model 3 Interface trial

Figure 10 Model 4 - Another approach to the User Interface.

As stated above this is a work in progress. Comments on the various models are welcome!

Community Engagement

Members of the RDA community were engaged at all stages of the tool prototype development process. Presentations were delivered and feedback was solicited from diverse stakeholders (researchers, data support professionals, software developers and funders) during the RDA's 20th Plenary in Gothenburg, 21st Plenary in Salzburg and 22nd virtual Plenary, in addition to the monthly WG meetings. Collaborative notes, meeting recordings and presentation slides are documented on the [WG landing page](#).

During such meetings, live demonstrations of the tool prototype features and functionalities were conducted, and feedback was solicited via open discussions. Feedback was collated and analysed by a WG subgroup to identify challenges and opportunities for improvement (see '[Key Findings](#)'). The categorisation schema of digital research tools ([Deliverable 2](#)) was also validated through extensive user feedback, confirming its accuracy and relevance as the foundation for the tool prototype.

Reporting and Recommendations

This document consolidates feedback from community engagement and formulates recommendations for future work and adoption strategies.

Key Findings

The development and community engagement processes yielded several important findings that highlight the value and potential impact of the online tool.

Tool Effectiveness

The prototype presents a foundation for an online tool that effectively maps digital research tools according to their features, functionalities, and relevance to the research data lifecycle. Based on feedback following live demonstrations of the tool prototype, users found its principles and approach compelling. It was described as intuitive and easy to navigate, enabling users to efficiently identify and explore different types of digital research tools for specific stages of the research data lifecycle.

Value to Stakeholders

Based on user feedback, the tool was deemed to provide value to the following stakeholders:

Researchers - *Enhanced ability to manage and share data.*

The tool provides researchers with a comprehensive resource for discovering and selecting suitable research tools, enhancing their ability to manage and share data effectively.

Data Managers - Improved understanding of the digital research data infrastructure.

Data support professionals benefit from an improved understanding of the digital research data infrastructure landscape, enabling them to provide more relevant and targeted support.

Tool Developers - Insights into tool features and interoperability.

Developers gain insights into the features, functionalities, and interoperability of different research tools, allowing them to improve their offerings.

Research Performing Organisations - Informed policy recommendations.

Organisations can make informed policy recommendations regarding the use of specific research tools for data management and sharing.

Funders and Publishers - Better guidance for data management practices.

Funders and publishers can provide better guidance to researchers and authors, ensuring that data management practices align with best practices and standards.

Feedback for Improvement

Users provided feedback on potential enhancements, such as additional filtering options, integration with other research platforms, and the inclusion of more tools in the database. It was also suggested that a follow-on RDA WG should research and explore other existing work undertaken to map the digital research data infrastructure landscape, and to harmonise efforts if suitable. User feedback also highlighted the importance of continuous updates to ensure the tool remains relevant and comprehensive.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and feedback gathered during the development and community engagement processes, the following recommendations are proposed:

Adoption and Integration

1. Facilitate and encourage widespread adoption of the tool by promoting the tool's value for research institutions, data management platforms, and relevant professional networks. Develop targeted outreach strategies to engage different stakeholder groups and highlight the tool's benefits, such as live demonstrations, webinars, conference presentations and posters.
2. Integrate the tool with existing digital research infrastructures to enhance its accessibility and usability. In particular, discuss synergies and potential integration with the Services and Tools Element of the GORC Model. Collaborate with other research tool developers and platform providers to facilitate seamless integration and data interoperability.

3. Identify an appropriate hosting platform for the tool. Since hosting costs will be minimal, it should be possible to identify a viable solution. Discuss with the Secretariat the possibility of hosting on the RDA website.

Continuous Improvement

4. Establish a process for regularly updating the tool's database to include new and emerging digital research tools. Monitor trends and advancements in digital research tools to ensure the tool remains current and relevant.
5. Continuously solicit feedback from users throughout the development and implementation process to identify areas for improvement and potential new features for user-driven enhancement. Implement a feedback loop to incorporate user suggestions and enhancements in future iterations of the tool.

Expanding Functionality

6. Enhance the tool's search and filtering capabilities to provide users with more granular control over their searches. Implement advanced filtering options based on specific criteria such as tool functionality, research domain, and compatibility/interoperability with other tools.
7. Explore opportunities for integrating the tool with other research management and data sharing platforms. Develop API functionalities to enable seamless data exchange and interoperability with external systems.

Educational and Support Resources

8. Develop comprehensive user guides and tutorials to assist users in navigating and utilising the tool effectively. Provide step-by-step instructions and best practice recommendations to enhance user experience based on stakeholder value and interest.
9. Organise generic training sessions and workshops to educate users about the tool's features and functionalities. Provide hands-on, practical training opportunities to help users become proficient in using the tool for their individual research data management needs.

Future Directions

Several strategic initiatives and future directions are proposed to build on the success of Deliverable 3, and ensure the ongoing development and impact of the online tool.

Database Expansion

Continuously expand the tool's database to include different types of digital research tools with relevant examples. Collaborate with tool developers and research communities to identify and categorise new tools.

Global Outreach

Promote the tool globally and establish partnerships with key stakeholders. Engage with international research communities and organisations to promote the tool and encourage global adoption. Establish partnerships with key stakeholders to facilitate knowledge sharing and collaboration.

Sustainability Plan

Develop a sustainability plan to ensure the long-term maintenance and support of the tool. Explore funding opportunities and collaborative ventures to secure the necessary resources for ongoing development.

Note: There has been ongoing discussion within the WG about the choice of software underpinning the online tool. The prototype presented herein currently uses open source software on open storage/facilities. It's coded entirely in R / Shiny with non commercial libraries. The WG should consider the future production status of the tools developed, and investigate the advantages and disadvantages of using different software. For example, should the final application be open or closed? What about the schema for the information stored? Should the storage layer be in a modern, stable environment like Oracle OCI or remain as a portable SQLite file?

Innovative Features

Investigate the potential for incorporating advanced features such as machine learning algorithms to provide personalised tool recommendations. Explore the integration of visualisation tools to enhance the user experience and provide insights into the research data lifecycle.

Next steps

Members of the WG and external collaborators are in the process of establishing a follow-on RDA WG to continue the development of the online tool. The focus of the follow-on WG will be to:

- **Continue development of the tool:** This will include the adding more information about the attributes of different types of digital research tools, such as whether they are open or closed source, disciplinary or agnostic, and, interoperable or not.
- **Explore sustainability of the model:** This will include ways in which it can be kept up to date to reflect changes in technology, development of new research tools,

changes in research practices, etc. Also provide options for continuing support for the model, which could include participation by various RDA groups and external organisations and/or communities.

- **Collaboration with RDA groups working on the Global Open Research Commons (GORC):** As the tool prototype was developed in recent months, the Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools WG had discussions with the [Global Open Research Commons IG](#) and [GORC International Model WG](#) about the synergies in work and potential for collaboration. Task Group 5 of the GORC International WG has undertaken an extensive [literature review](#) and released a [Commons Attributes Model \(Version 0.5\)](#) that identifies a suite of services and tools that will inform the work of this WG. Efforts to describe the features, functionality, and interoperability of different types of research tools will complement the development of the ‘Commons Integration Roadmap’ (GORC WG Deliverable) by providing key information about different types of research tools, and highlighting areas for the improvement of their interoperability and user experience.

Conclusion

Deliverable 3 has successfully developed a prototype for an interactive online tool that maps digital research tools to the research data lifecycle.

This tool provides significant value to researchers, data managers, tool developers, research organisations, funders, and publishers. The comprehensive feedback from the RDA community has been instrumental in refining the tool and ensuring its relevance and usability.

The recommendations and future directions outlined in this deliverable report offer a roadmap for continued development, adoption, and impact. By leveraging the work achieved by the current WG, as well as the insights and feedback gathered for the creation of this deliverable, a follow-on RDA WG is well-positioned to enhance the tool’s functionality and expand its reach, ultimately contributing to the advancement of digital research data management and sharing practices.

For further details, please refer to the [RDA-OfR Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools WG](#).

Contributors

	Name	Affiliation	ORCID
1	Adam Vials Moore	Jisc	0000-0002-2085-1908
2	Marcelo Garcia	King Abdullah University of Science and Technology (KAUST)	0000-0002-2927-2371

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for Research

3	Rory Macneil	Research Space	0000-0002-8429-096X
4	Richard Pitts	Oracle for Research	0000-0002-2037-3360